

Advances in herbivore-induced plant volatiles (HIPVs) as plant defense and application potential for crop protection

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Plants release volatile compounds called herbivore-induced plant volatiles (HIPVs) in response to being eaten by herbivores. These compounds play crucial roles in plant defense, either by repelling the herbivores themselves or by enticing the herbivores' natural enemies, such as predatory insects, to attack the plant. Insect parasitoids and predators rely on HIPVs to find their prey or host, and when a plant recruits these mutualistic insects, it is protected against herbivores. Yet, numerous fields of study have lately begun to focus on HIPVs for crop protection beyond their role in tritrophic interaction.

Synopsis of the initial data on relationships between the three trophic levels (tritrophic interaction)

Plants can use the third trophic level (natural enemies) to protect themselves from herbivores by: dispensing volatile chemicals that affect arthropod foraging behavior; using companion plants that affect the attraction of pests and beneficial insects (such as applying in stimulo-deterrent diversionary (push-pull strategies); and forming mutualistic relationships with other plants.

The HIPVs groups

While there is a wide variety of HIPVs produced by different plant species, there is also a lot of overlap between plant taxonomic groups. HIPVs could be terpenoids, green leaf volatiles (GLV), or fatty acid derivatives. They could also be benzenoids/phenylpropanoids, C5-branched compounds, or different compounds with nitrogen and Sulphur.

HIPVs for plant defense

Through the process of co-evolution, plant and insect insects have developed both harmful and helpful interactions with one another. Potentially harmful insect herbivores pose a significant risk to plants during plant-insect interactions. Pestilential insects that feed on herbivorous plants. The plants have been forced to mount a defensive response to the onslaught of enemies. They can't run away from

herbivores that attack because they're firmly planted in the earth. Thus, they have developed a wide variety of defense mechanisms to fend off herbivores.

Indirect defense and HIPVS as a resource for arthropod predators and parasites

Indirect defense of plants against arthropod herbivores by HIPVs has been well-documented. Herbivore-induced secondary metabolites (HIPVs) generated from herbivore-damaged plants contain several chemical components that attract arthropod natural enemies, either singly or in combination. Herbivore species, herbivore developmental instar, plant tissue, and abiotic circumstances can all affect the makeup of the HIPVs, which can consist of anywhere from tens to more than two hundred chemicals. A number of electrophysiological and behavioral investigations have shown that arthropod natural enemies use HIPVs for their own benefit, either to detect food or host in simple or complex vegetation, or to act as a "bodyguard" for plants. The HIPVs are a 'scream' for help from the herbivores' natural enemies, warning nearby plants of an impending attack. These plant "screams" serve as "dinner bells" for parasitoid and predatory arthropods, which then flock to the plants in search of the signaled food (herbivore). An indirect method of plant defense against harmful herbivores.

HIPVs and direct defense

HIPVS could also play a direct role in plant defense by stopping insects from feeding or laying eggs or by making them poisonous so they can't do either. They could also protect plants from pathogens. Several plants release HIPVs in response to herbivore attack; some of them, such (E)-caryophyllene, have been shown to be effective against diseases, and others, like indole, are harmful to caterpillars. Herbivore-impacting volatiles (HIPVs) released by plants in response to herbivore damage may have a repellent effect because of their direct harmful impact on herbivores. Nonetheless, interesting evidence suggests that HIPVs make plant natural enemies and some specialized herbivores more visible.

Substances that cause HIPVs are used to entice predatory insects to attack

It may be more effective to use chemicals that encourage the formation of HIPVs to draw in these predators. Examples of such products include dispensers containing the plant defense stimulant methyl salicylate (Me SA), as well as other insect attractants. Although Me SA has a repellency effect on some parasitoids, it also inhibits the release of some HIPVs (which are induced by chemicals other than MeSA) that serve to attract predators. However, this can be circumvented by administering more HIPVs-inducing chemicals or elicitors to the plants.

Utilize volatiles from companion plants to repel pests and attract predators

It is possible to establish parallels between the use of HIPVs and the use of companion plants for pest management in crop production, with the latter typically employed in push-pull tactics that rely on plant scents to discourage insect pests from settling among crop fields. The most common example of this strategy in action is the planting of forage grasses like Napier grass, *Pennisetum purpureum* Schumach (Poaceae), or Sudan grass (*Vulgare sudanaense*), along the field edges with a forage legume like silver leaf desmodium (*Desmodium* spp) (push plant) (which also fixes nitrogen for crops and inhibits the notorious striga weed). The push plant's volatiles deter ovipositing insect pests like stem borers and fall armyworm from the maize crop and draw in natural enemies, while the pull plant's

volatiles lure the ovipositing females away from the crop, causing the "pull," which is fatal to the pest's offspring.

Creation of Insect Odor Detection Devices

In addition to the aforementioned applications of HIPVs for pest management, it is also possible that in the future, olfactory sensors might be developed to detect herbivore infestations by the use of specific herbivore-induced plant volatiles. There are new tools being developed that will enable for the monitoring of volatile emissions in real time. In this case, it seems that physiochemically-based sensors would be the best option. Recent advances in proton transfer reaction mass spectrometry (PTR-MS) are quite encouraging. Direct chemical ionization of headspace volatiles is used in PTR-MS for real-time detection of volatile organic compounds, and the potential of this technology has been substantially increased with the advent of PTR-time of flight-MS (PTR-TOF-MS), which provides higher resolution and sensitivity.

Conclusion

Recent studies on HIPVs have expanded into the multidisciplinary realm of insect-plant interactions and pest control. Much literature has been compiled on the ecological significance of HIPVs, including the functions it plays in attracting natural enemies in both simple tritrophic interactions and more complicated interactions. By doing so, we can pave the way for the development of similarly new and sustainable pest management solutions by learning more about the biochemical, molecular, and behavioral ecology of arthropod-plant interactions.